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Scientific synthesis

Leaving latency and moving manifest: understanding and resolving inertia

6.1 WIDELY RESENTED, YET WIDELY NEGLECTED

This dissertation started out with a sense of wonder at the lack of action regarding a widely resented and ecologically significant threat, posed by the persistently invading alien Coralita vine on the Caribbean islands Saba and St. Eustatius. How to square the alarm among ecologists and locals about the ever-spreading pink flowers with the inertia on the side of government and community alike? Environmental governance literature is well capable of explaining a lack of action regarding phenomena that people do not acknowledge as problematic, but Coralita certainly is an infamous and disliked phenomenon by all these actors. Hence the research question of this dissertation:

How can the policy and management inertia regarding the invasive alien Coralita vine on Saba and St. Eustatius be explained and resolved?

In the foregoing chapters, several explanations were discussed and avenues to resolving the absence of action offered. Chapter 2 showed how a polycentric governance arrangement on paper may in practice hamper policy development when the division of budgets and responsibilities are unclear. Stakeholders have trouble articulating their perceptions regarding Coralita due to a lack of knowledge on its impacts, as discussed in chapter 3. These two factors contribute to what is referred to as policy inertia. A second element of the lack of action was discussed in chapters 4 and 5, namely management inertia due to the problem's latent problem status. In section 6.2, both types of inertia are elaborated on, followed by a discussion of latency as a problem status, which answers the first part of the research question. The second part of the research question is answered in section 6.3, and two avenues for resolving the lack of action by lifting the policy and management inertia offered.

6.2 EXPLAINING THE LACK OF ACTION: POLICY AND MANAGEMENT INERTIA

Understanding why a given environmental issue is not acted upon is one of the major themes in environmental governance literature, and explanations range from deliberate to unintentional reasons for not acting. For example, the benefits of acting can be lower than the costs, rendering it rational to not act (Munck af Rosenschöld et al. 2014). Another deliberate type of not acting is what Bachrach and Baratz (1963) call a non-decision, when a community knows that existing authorities, powers and values will keep them from addressing the issue. Alternatively, not acting can be unintentional, resulting from an impasse (sensu Biesbroek et al. 2014) or gridlock (sensu Jones and Baumgartner 2012), both following from incompatible or opposing interests and opinions. Similarly, inertia

can occur in a situation where the pressure to adapt does not outweigh the pressure to continue extant institutional routines. Giezen (2013) defines this as: "(...) the inability to make a change when it is required or when it would be beneficial (...)" (Giezen 2013, 726). The inertia analyzed in this dissertation sits somewhere in between: the latency of the problem renders acting disadvantageous, yet the current manifestation of the vine is not the result of deliberate (not) acting, but rather emanates as a corollary to land-use practices it is embedded in. For the purpose of this dissertation, a distinction was made between policy inertia and management inertia. The former pertains to the design, development, or implementation of policy; the latter looks at on the ground management activities, aiming to control Coralita. In the following sections both types of inertia as encountered on Saba and Statia are analyzed.

6.2.1 Why is there policy inertia?

A clear absence of policy regarding Coralita on Saba and Statia was found, as discussed in chapter 2, despite the highly polycentric governance configurations of the respective islands and the Kingdom of the Netherlands. This observation seems at odds with the literature on polycentric configurations, that asserts polycentricity enhances the adaptiveness and robustness of governance arrangements (Folke et al. 2005, Pahl-Wostl and Knieper 2014, Marshall et al. 2016), motivates voluntary cooperation (Marshall 2009) and has potential to outperform larger centrally controlled arrangements (Ostrom et al. 1961, Andersson and Ostrom 2008). On paper, the governance configuration is quite high up the polycentric spectrum: there is a strong overarching system, within which the islands push vehemently for autonomous decision-making. From a polycentric perspective, the autonomy allows for adjusting policy to local circumstances, while the overarching system safeguards the coherence between all entities; this should be conducive to developing the most appropriate policy to tackle a problem such as Coralita. And indeed, for the French Caribbean overseas territories, the overarching system ensures that environmental goals are reached, and provides the resources for the local entities to do so. The French islands have the liberty to spend these resources however they deem fit for reaching the goals set by the overarching system. But in the Dutch case, the role of the overarching system (i.e., The Netherlands) is less clear. Since the governance configuration's inception in 2010, the islands have pushed for more autonomy, while at the same time the overarching system has enhanced its regulations. Goals regarding IAS management were set by the overarching system, but the islands claim the resources needed for realizing these are not provided. The uncertainty about the division of responsibilities and mandates, and their concomitant budgetary arrangements, results in policy inertia: the development of policy is virtually suspended until these matters are clarified.

This policy inertia is compounded by an absence of clear stakeholders to exert pressure on policy makers, and whose perspectives can be involved in policy development. The existence of actors that self-identify as stakeholders is typically presumed in the environmental governance literature. This is reflected in a wide range of literature available on stakeholder analysis and involvement methodology (e.g. Vassilides and Jensen 2016, Lopes and Videira 2016). Sometimes, stakeholders' preferences are acknowledged to be unarticulated, but the approaches assume that these can be elicited to identify stakeholders nonetheless (e.g., Tompkins et al. 2008). Challenging that assumption, chapter 3 argues that when the impacts of an environmental problem on livelihoods are unclear, stakeholders' problem perceptions are rendered latent. This is problematic since constituency pressure is necessary to push politicians to take action, and stakeholder involvement is required for developing relevant and legitimate policies on IAS and for ensuring implementation and compliance (Sharp et al. 2011, Shackleton and Shackleton 2016, Niemiec et al. 2016).

The explanation of policy inertia lies thus with dynamics within the polycentric governance arrangements and the latency of stakeholder perceptions. Yet, this does not preclude management of the vine by individual community members, as happens often when a formal institution is not fulfilling its role (Sullivan et al. 2017). But aside from a few sporadic clearings, no evidence of community initiatives regarding the removal or containment of Coralita on both islands was found: how to explain this management inertia?

6.2.2 Why is there management inertia?

Why Coralita manifests itself on Saba the way it does, was explained in chapter 4 through an aggregate of practices and sticking points that produces a vicious cycle of free-roaming goats, limited agricultural activity and large stretches of unused land, offering plenty of area for Coralita to spread. Notwithstanding important differences between the islands, most notably regarding agricultural activity, these practices and sticking points have explanatory value for Coralita's manifestation on Statia as well. On both islands, about 90% of land is privately owned and spatial planning regulations are absent. Statia has a spatial planning ordinance, but its status is unclear and it does not stipulate anything about IAS management (Island Council St. Eustatius 2011). Saba does not have such a plan, and citizens are very wary of any restrictions pertaining to private land, as land is considered a major asset (Schoenmaeckers 2010). In that setting, regulation from the government imposing restrictions or obligations regarding IAS on private land is highly unlikely to be developed. Thus, it is up to the land owners themselves to manage Coralita. Given the widely voiced dismay about the vine and worry about its continuous spread, one would expect efforts from private landowners to contain and remove Coralita from their land. But during the four years of fieldwork for this disserta-

tion, only a few sporadic cleaning efforts were found. How to explain this management inertia?

When a community is not acting on an environmental issue, a common diagnosis on the part of environmental governance scholars is a lack of awareness among community members. Either they are ignorant about the problem and the risks it entails (e.g., Esteve et al. 2018, Fizer et al. 2018), or their value system does not afford the problem sufficient attention (e.g., Joubert and Davidson 2010). Either way, efforts focus on getting people to understand and acknowledge the problem at hand. But chapter 4 offered an alternative explanation of a community's lack of action, namely the latent problem status of the environmental problem. Latency was defined as comprising highly uncertain impacts and posing little threat to livelihoods, as opposed to a manifest status when impacts are very predictable and pose a large threat to livelihoods. This dissertation argues that for problems with a latent status, inertia on the side of the community is not attributable to the community's perceptions or awareness. Rather, it pertains to the problem itself: if the problem does not pose a threat to livelihoods and there is a shortage of knowledge, a community is not inclined to act. Chapter 4 illustrated this by showing how the aggregate of practices in which a problem is embedded is not adjusted by a community, in spite of general weariness regarding that problem. Encouraging the community to act should thus not focus on raising awareness or adjusting perspectives, but deal with the shortage of knowledge available and threats posed to livelihoods. In section 6.3 it is discussed how to encourage communities faced with latent problems to act, but first we look at the result of the policy and management inertia as they interact.

6.2.3 Interplay of policy and management inertia

Summing up, dynamics within the polycentric governance configuration, and the latent problem status of Coralita result in policy and management inertia. Jointly, these two types of inertia mean that no changes are made to the current manifestation of Coralita following from the daily land-use practices of Saban and Statian community. This is the central explanatory argument of this dissertation, as depicted in Figure 15. It shows policy inertia following from uncertainties in the governance configuration, which was discussed in chapter 2, and from the lack of readily identifiable stakeholders, as discussed in chapter 3. Management inertia is shown to follow from the latent problem status as well, as discussed in chapter 4. And due to these inertias, Coralita is left to grow where it grows. Feeding into these three explanatory clusters is a cluster of daily land-use practices of the community, which were discussed for Saba in chapter 4. These affect Coralita's current manifestation by providing large stretches of unused land to cover, and add to inertia through the high costs of acting on Coralita. Next to that, the practices affect the latency of the problem, as the low threat Coralita poses to livelihoods on both islands follows from the land-use practices, which contribute to

the limited agricultural activity. In turn, the practices are affected by the other three explanatory clusters: Coralita's presence and the inertia pertaining to it, exacerbate the lack of land-use. Also, the uncertainties in the governance configuration mean little spatial planning and land-use restrictions exist, allowing the practices to persist. Lastly, the explanatory clusters affect each other in two other ways. One, Coralita's current manifestation adds to the latent problem status, as it downplays the potential impacts: people see it growing on unused land and experience little negative impacts from it. Secondly, the policy and management inertia allow the uncertainties in the governance configuration and the latent problem status to persist. Thus, a vicious cycle results, but in section 6.3 suggestions for breaking through that cycle will be made.

Figure 15. Dynamics addressed in this dissertation regarding Coralita on Saba and St. Eustatius, with three explanatory clusters (in grey) and the cluster of daily practices (in blue).

The foregoing explains the specific case of inertia regarding Coralita on Saba and Statia, as was the purview of this dissertation. It is not asserted to be generalizable to every case of inertia regarding an invasive alien species, since many other elements can be at play. However, the basic dynamic of problem status affecting inertia, and inertia affecting a species' manifestation, can be assumed to feature regarding every invasive alien species. How it plays out exactly, and what the links with the governance configuration, daily practices and possibly other elements are, will differ per species. What does this insight add to extant environmental governance literature on addressing problems?

6.2.4 Scientific contribution in analyzing inertia

One of the main theoretical contributions of this dissertation consists of the analysis of policy and management inertia, in terms of problem statuses defined by the predictability of impacts and threats posed to livelihoods. To relay these statuses in a structured way, chapter 4 depicted them as a grid made up of two dimensions which result in four quadrants, as depicted in Figure 16. The four quadrants represent the status an environmental problem can have at one point in time, and in section 4.2.1, some examples of how environmental problems currently fit into this grid were discussed. Two main assertions were made regarding this grid. One, that for non-manifest problems, typical environmental management tools are unsuitable. Conventional stakeholder analysis and participatory action research approaches do not work, and chapter 3 and 4 offered alternatives. Two, these statuses are dynamic instead of inherent to a problem, meaning they can change over time: e.g., scientific progress might enhance the predictability of impacts, or changes in livelihoods could decrease or aggravate the threat a problem poses. In chapter 5, three trajectories between the problem statuses were illustrated, and below in section 6.3 suggestions for promoting such shifts will be made. But first, this typology is compared to other thinking in environmental governance on why certain environmental problems do get attention while others do not. Also, the implications of perceiving invasive alien species through this typology are discussed.

Figure 16. Typology of problem statuses for environmental problems, as defined by the predictability of their impacts on the vertical axis, and the threat they pose to livelihoods on the horizontal axis. This results in four quadrants, representing statuses an environmental problem can have at a given point in time.

6.2.4.1 *Not every situation is a problem*

The explanation as offered in this dissertation for the lack of action regarding Coralita despite it being considered a nuisance, revolves around the latent problem status it has on Saba and Statia. That is not to say that there are no other factors at play; it is not intended to be an exhaustive explanation for the inertia regarding Coralita. For example, daily practices and sticking points thereof in which Coralita is embedded, were discussed in chapter 4. But the idea that a latent problem status contributes to management and policy inertia, jointly hampering adjustments to Coralita's current manifestation, is novel. It is an important contribution to other theories such as Advocacy coalition theory or Punctuated equilibrium theory, which are used in political theory to explain why some problems attract attention and make it to the political agenda while others do not. The main difference between these theories and the problem status typology as presented in this dissertation, lies in the explanatory onus: instead of the actors and political arena dealing with the problem, it is on the characteristics of the problem itself. The perspectives are not mutually exclusive, so there is potential for integrating the thinking in terms of a problem's status with these political theories. How would these theories explain the inertia regarding Coralita, and what does the problem status thinking add to that?

Political decision-making is generally regarded a somewhat chaotic affair, depending more on who is paying attention to what when, than the costs and benefits of the potential decisions. Also, problems are considered to be a construct: they do not exist as such, but have to be defined first: "The difference between a condition and a problem is that the latter is seen as something that we ought to do something about (...)" (Knagård 2015, 452). Why the situation of Coralita is not a problem, is explained differently by different theories. For example, Punctuated equilibrium theory, with as main authors Jones and Baumgartner (2005), looks at agenda-setting through the lens of winning and losing coalitions. Which coalition is the winning one depends on the image they propagate of "their" problem, and the venue in which problems are being addressed at that moment. They would thus say that Coralita is not on the agenda since the coalition that propagates an image of Coralita as a problem is on the losing end. Hence, it receives little attention from the people who are capable of putting it on the agenda.

Coalitions are also central to the Advocacy coalition framework (Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith 1993). They argue that people hold deep core beliefs and are arranged in coalitions according to their policy beliefs. These coalitions retain resources and power, and the policy beliefs of the coalition that holds most of these, dominate the political arena and get translated into policy action. Why Coralita does not get addressed would by this theory be explained as an absence of it in the policy beliefs of the coalition that holds the relevant resources for addressing it.

Instead of coalitions, Multiple streams theory would point to Coralita being absent from the relevant streams. Kingdon and Zahriadis are prominent authors on this theory,

and distinguish between a problem stream, a policy stream and a politics stream. When these are connected on a certain topic, a problem ends up on the agenda. This can happen during what is called a policy window, and the connecting of streams is done by policy entrepreneurs. But first, a problem needs to be recognized, i.e., to feature in a problem stream. Some recent literature has zoomed in on the problem stream and how topics compete for attention therein. Whether a situation, condition or phenomenon becomes recognized as a problem, is something that happens in the problem stream. Mukherjee and Howlett (2015) contend that within the problem stream, epistemic communities exist, consisting of actors involved in delimiting and articulating problem spaces. Based on a shared interpretation of knowledge, an epistemic community shapes discourses and "(...) pursue[s] the translation of broad issues into distinct problems that policymakers can act upon (...)" (Mukherjee and Howlett 2015, 70). Knaggård (2015) ascribes this type of activities to one specific actor: the problem broker frames a condition as a public problem without promoting a specific solution. They aim to get policy makers to accept their framing, for which they require access, credibility and persistence. Reardon (2018) argues for a view of networks as developing, framing and sustaining ideas that facilitate and constrain the recognition of problems. Within a network, the dominant coalition develops an appreciative system, comprising factual and value judgements through which problems are perceived and delimited.

Through these lenses, Coralita may not be recognized as a problem for two reasons: because there is no problem broker, epistemic community or appreciative system that frames it as such within a problem stream; or because the Coralita problem stream does not get coupled with the other streams. The question that remains unanswered by each of these theories, is why that is not the case. This is where the thinking in terms of a problem's status makes an important contribution to environmental governance literature. The typology acknowledges that some situations are more likely to be recognized as problems than others. An environmental problem that has a latent status, is not very likely to be picked up by a problem broker or feature in the policy beliefs of the dominant coalition. Opposed to this, a manifest problem is much more likely to feature in a dominant coalition's policy beliefs or to get the attention of an epistemic community. This dissertation thus explains a phase preceding the purview of the theories discussed above. Next to these insights into environmental problems, what does this dissertation add to literature on invasive alien species?

6.2.4.2 Implications for conceptualization of invasive alien species

This thesis framed an IAS as a problem comprising two dimensions: the threat it poses to livelihoods, and the predictability of its impacts. This departs from conceptualizations commonly used in invasion literature, such as the barrier models presented by e.g., Blackburn et al. (2011) or Richardson et al. (2000). Chapter 5 discussed that the "invasive

alien” label does not so much give rise to action regarding invasive alien species, as it is an additional argument for acting. For the Asian tiger mosquito and the Egyptian goose in the Netherlands, their status as an alien was invoked to tighten the control. But the main incentive for controlling them, were the hazards they are from a health and infrastructural perspective, respectively. Thus, while the “invasive alien” label is reflective of an ecological reality, it holds little relevance from a governance perspective. For the governance reality of an invasive alien species, the two dimensions mentioned earlier are what mediate action: threat to livelihoods and predictability of impacts. Both dimensions will be discussed below and compared to common conceptualizations of IAS, starting with the threat posed to livelihoods.

Impacts of an IAS are generally what gives rise to research and governance efforts regarding a species, but are also highly contested. As discussed in chapter 1, both the ecosystem dynamics resulting in an impact and the subjective valuation of these, are fraught with ambiguity, uncertainty and knowledge gaps. To establish a threat posed to a community’s livelihood, a very limited amount of information regarding the working of the ecosystem and the effect of the IAS on it, is needed. Rather, a basic understanding of the community’s livelihood is required, which is most often readily available or fairly easily obtainable. For Coralita, knowledge on the impacts on nutrient cycles, water table and soil stability is lacking. But knowing the limited role of agriculture in livelihoods of the island communities suffices to deem Coralita a limited threat to livelihoods.

The second dimension of the dissertation’s conceptualization of IAS, the predictability of impacts, makes the uncertainty surrounding most IAS an explicit part of its definition. Also, the profound character of that uncertainty, that is referred to as “ignorance” in risk literature (Liu et al. 2011), is stressed. Uncertainty surrounding IAS has long been acknowledged, but approaches to dealing with it assume that at least the suite of potential impacts is known. E.g., deliberative multi-criteria analysis (Liu et al. 2010, Liu et al. 2011) acknowledges uncertainties and ambiguities, but assumes that impacts can always be assessed and evaluated, and calls for citizen juries to weigh the uncertainties. This dissertation has shown an example of where the uncertainty is so profound, that no citizen jury is able to assess it in a meaningful manner. Similarly, other difficulties in dealing with the invasive species resulting from the high uncertainties were demonstrated, such as latent stakeholder perceptions and community inertia. Literature on IAS so far has not recognized the uncertainty regarding an IAS for the crucial dimension it is, which this typology aims to correct.

By combining these two dimensions, threat to livelihoods and predictability of the impacts, the typology presented in this dissertation judges a species by its status as a problem: latent, manifest, or somewhere in between. Latency was linked to management and policy inertia, while a manifest status appeared conducive to action. Regarding an invasive alien species with a latent problem status, stakeholder positions can therefore

be expected to be unclear, and inertia regarding policy and management expected to exist. How to deal with this was discussed in chapter 3 and 4, which will be reflected on in the next section.

6.3 RESOLVING THE LACK OF ACTION

The research aim of this dissertation was not only to explain the lack of action regarding Coralita on Saba and Statia, but also to provide ways of resolving it. Although already touched upon in several of the chapters, the legitimacy of wanting to redeem that lack of action is worth mentioning again. For one, Saba and Statia are located in the Caribbean, and as such part of one of the world's biodiversity hotspots, with about 60% of the region's 12,000 plant species being endemic (Mittermeier et al. 1998, Kairo et al. 2003). Secondly, invasive alien species (IAS) are, after habitat loss, the second biggest threat to biodiversity (Pejchar and Mooney 2009). This threat is even higher on islands, since insular ecosystems are particularly fragile, and IAS are claimed to be more likely to establish successfully and have a more devastating impact, there (Kairo et al. 2003, Reaser et al. 2007). Although the specific dynamics are challenged (e.g., Sax 2008, Vilà et al. 2011), this is definitely cause for vigilance. Thirdly, preventive action regarding IAS is regarded as the most effective and the least costly approach (Russell et al. 2017). One estimate even contends that every dollar spent on prevention, saves 17 dollars in later measures (Davies and Sheley 2007). Jointly, these reasons make a lack of action regarding IAS on Saba and Statia worrisome, and legitimize attempts at resolving the inertia. This dissertation does not aim for a specific course of action, but for anything other than not-acting by default. As discussed in chapter 4, inertia regarding Coralita is not the result of a conscious choice not to act, but emanates as a corollary to land-use practices. In light of the large potential impacts of the vine, deliberateness in dealings with it should be strived for. This dissertation offers handles for that, addressing the explanatory dynamics expounded in section 6.2.3 and Figure 15 in several ways:

- The polycentric governance configuration can be improved based on the findings relayed in chapter 2, foregrounding the division of responsibilities and budget;
- How to make latent problem perceptions explicit was shown in chapter 3, through a combination of Q methodology and a landscape value typology. This way, stakeholders regarding a latent problem can nevertheless be identified;
- The problem status of Coralita on Saba and Statia could be moved from latent towards manifest, for which chapter 5 described trajectories applicable to invasive alien species in general. Also, chapter 4 showed how through PAR-L, a latent problem can be addressed as a corollary to a manifest problem;

- The daily practices were addressed during the PAR-L process in chapter 4 as well, and recommendations for enhancing that on Saba and Statia will be made in chapter 7.

The recurring topic here is Coralita's latent problem status, which as depicted in Figure 15 feeds into both the policy and management inertia. Changing that problem status would presumably redeem these inertias. This section looks into two approaches to lifting Coralita's latency, in concordance with the two axes of the problem status grid (see Figure 16), which places Coralita at the bottom of a vertical axis representing the predictability of impacts, and at the left end of a horizontal axis representing the threat to livelihoods (see Figure 16). Following the logic of this grid, efforts should be directed at maximizing the predictability of the impacts and the threat posed to livelihoods. In this section, suggestions will be done for how to go about this, starting with the vertical axis.

6.3.1 Enhancing predictability of impacts

To enhance the predictability, i.e., move an environmental problem up along the vertical axis, two elements are important: the additional data needed to enhance predictability, i.e., content of remaining knowledge gap; and the type of knowledge required. Regarding content, ideally whatever knowledge gaps regarding processes and parameters exist are filled. Research efforts would be such that full impact and risk assessments can be completed, such as Harmonia⁺ (D'hondt et al. 2014) or SEICAT (Bacher et al. 2017). However, before embarking on a comprehensive data-gathering campaign, some considerations regarding the type of knowledge required should be addressed. Within IAS literature, researchers increasingly stress the need to broaden the scope of the knowledge that is produced, arguing that objective ecological science is not the only type required (e.g., Larson 2007). Since invasive species have impacts on people and managing them can have impacts too, scientists cannot refrain from participating in deliberations involving value judgements. Disregarding socio-political context, or unidirectional communication have been found to foster conflict (Crowley et al. 2017), and knowledge produced needs to fit a community's value systems (Moon et al. 2015). Byers et al. (2002) provide an example of the Zebra mussel, arguing that despite the large body of scientific literature available, nature managers were not prepared for dealing with the invasive species. In the field of climate change, this has been dubbed the 'climate information usability gap' (Lemos et al. 2012). Yet, despite the growing call for socially relevant science, IAS studies remain predominantly focused on ecological data (Estévez et al. 2015). Knowledge gathering efforts to enhance the predictability of impacts should thus move beyond purely ecological data and involve the societal context in which management would take place, to prevent a mismatch between scientific knowledge and political reality.

A helpful perspective on this might be offered by the three characteristics of effective information regarding environmental themes, as distinguished by Cash et al. (2003): legitimacy, credibility and salience. Credibility is dependent on scientific soundness of the data and reasoning; legitimacy on representing stakeholders' divergent values and beliefs and being unbiased in its conduct and fair in its treatment of opposing views; salience is the relevance of the information to the decision makers (Cash et al. 2003, Van Enst et al. 2014). Just like Van Enst et al. (2014) linked these different types of knowledge needs to different interaction problems between science and politics, they can be linked to the four problem statuses distinguished in this dissertation. For a latent problem, all three types of knowledge are lacking. When focusing knowledge generating efforts on credible knowledge such as purely ecological data, the problem evolves from being latent towards conceptual. When mainly gathering legitimate data, for example on stakeholder positions, the problem moves towards a tangible problem status. When gathering both legitimate and credible knowledge, the problem status of an environmental problem moves from latent to manifest. However, additional salient information, i.e., information that fits policy processes, remains needed as long as the problem exists. Data-gathering efforts should thus aim to gather all three types of data.

But, if the research setting is such that the lack of knowledge cannot be redeemed within the span of the project, as was the case for this dissertation, chapter 3 suggested how to work around that knowledge gap. The approach comes down to circumventing the lack of knowledge regarding Coralita's impacts by focusing on hypothetical impacts. Participants articulated their views regarding hypothetical impacts of Coralita, eliciting stakeholder groups based on potential impacts of the vine. For this, interviews were conducted using Q methodology and a landscape value typology that informed the statements presented to the participants. By discussing hypothetical impacts, the low predictability of Coralita's impacts contributing to its latency was circumvented. This allows for the identification of stakeholders and contributes to lifting policy inertia.

Solely moving up along the vertical axis can advance a latent problem towards a conceptual problem status. However, as illustrated in chapter 5, a manifest problem status is more conducive to action. The next section will therefore look at how to achieve movement along the horizontal axis, i.e., towards a tangible problem status.

6.3.2 Enhancing link with livelihoods

The horizontal axis of the problem status grid (Figure 16) depicts the threat a species poses to a community's livelihoods. To move along the horizontal axis, a threat does not need to be created in a physical sense, but by adjusting the problem frame. In chapter 4 an approach for doing so, PAR-L, was designed and illustrated. This approach starts by shifting focus to a more manifest problem, with links to the latent problem. The project should then be designed in such a way that when addressing the manifest problem,

the latent problem is addressed as a corollary. In chapter 4, by addressing the manifest problem of agriculture, the latent problem of Coralita was dealt with simultaneously.

Alternatively, an effort could be made to gather more stakeholder-relevant, i.e., legitimate knowledge, regarding the topic at hand, as discussed above. When aiming for a shift along the horizontal axis of the problem typology grid, instead of research into ecological questions, matters that are of interest to the community could be researched, such as the best management methods regarding Coralita, or specific potential impacts of the vine that people find explicitly worrisome, as identified in chapter 3. Such legitimate knowledge would award Coralita more of a tangible problem status, rather than a latent problem status. Moreover, when evaluating the pilot conducted in chapter 4, participants indicated the need for such research efforts, to address knowledge needs that became apparent during the pilot. The tailor-made character of PAR-L projects renders them very suitable for incorporating research efforts, for example via approaches such as joint knowledge production (Hegger et al. 2012) and socially robust science (Seijger et al. 2016), that facilitate the involvement of stakeholders' questions, knowledge and interests into scientific efforts.

The reasoning behind aiming for a more manifest problem status, is that involvement of stakeholders is easier for a manifest problem than a latent one, since there is more at stake for them. Which also means that conflicts may arise, when stakes are contradictory. Chapter 5 showed how conflict indeed increases for a manifest problem, but action as well. The conflict that arose was even partially due to the type of action undertaken, and not solely regarding opposing stakes. Thus, when moving along the horizontal axis towards a tangible or manifest problem status, arrangements to deal with conflict should be made. As mentioned in chapter 1, approaches such as community-based polycentricity and co-design are touted within invasion science as best capable of facilitating opposing stakes and building the social capital required to deal with these (Marshall et al. 2016, Shackleton et al. 2019). In a way, PAR-L is even more stakeholder-centered than such co-management approaches, since the community decides on the topic that will be the focus of the co-management efforts. Thus, PAR-L should be well capable of dealing with contradicting stakes, should any arise when a latent problem moves towards a manifest status.

In sum, changing the problem status of an environmental problem from latent to conceptual or tangible, could take shape as a PAR-L project with an explicit research component. The research should generate knowledge that increases the predictability of impacts of the problem, but is relevant to the community as well. Focusing on hypothetical impacts of the problem and linking with extant problems that pose a threat to livelihoods, was shown in this dissertation to lift a community's inertia, despite the latency of a problem.

6.3.3 Scientific contribution in resolving inertia

In addressing the second part of the research question – on how the inertia regarding Coralita on Saba and Statia can be resolved – lies another theoretical contribution of this dissertation. Namely, to link inertia to the status of a problem and frame the resolving of inertia also in terms of changing the problem status. This differs from conventional approaches to resolving inertia, which typically focus on adjusting perceptions or raising awareness. For example, Sullivan et al. (2017) speak of how trust should be enhanced, so resource users and government actors will be better capable of managing the invasive mile-a-minute weed (*Mikani amicantha*) in Nepal. To enhance trust, the authors recommend addressing issues that directly affect the resource users' daily lives. But what if the issue that needs addressing does not affect the community's daily lives? This dissertation argues for targeting a problem's status in order to resolve inertia, rather than the actors refraining from acting. To do so, a problem can be made more manifest, or focus can be shifted towards a problem with a more manifest status, as discussed earlier. The benefit of this approach is that it harnesses extant inclinations towards acting, rather than trying to break through resistance. It shifts the purpose of a project from getting people to act on something they do not care about, towards something that does interest them and regarding which stakes exist to build on. The suggestions for how to do that, constitute two methodological contributions of this dissertation: the use of Q methodology combined with a landscape value typology, and the PAR-L approach. Both were explicitly designed for dealing with inertia regarding a latent problem, but some of their characteristics can be helpful in other cases as well.

6.3.3.1 Methodological contribution: Q methodology

To resolve the latency of stakeholder perspectives, stakeholder perceptions regarding a phenomenon linked to the issue of interest were elicited. As discussed in the analysis of inertia regarding Coralita, one of the contributing factors to policy inertia are these latent stakeholder perceptions (see section 6.2.1). Chapter 3 addressed that issue, analyzing that the lack of knowledge regarding Coralita hampered the articulation of opinions regarding the species, resulting in an absence of clear stakeholder groups. A creative approach was developed to elicit stakeholder perspectives nonetheless, by conducting interviews employing Q methodology regarding landscape values. Regarding these landscape values, participants do have manifest perspectives, as well as regarding hypothetical impacts of Coralita on these values. Thus, three perspectives on potential Coralita impacts were elicited for each island, that can be built on for stakeholder involvement efforts. This way, the policy inertia can be resolved.

Q methodology is typically used to map discourses, reveal value patterns or build a shared value system (Ellis et al. 2007, Webler et al. 2009, Gruber 2011, Uittenbroek et al. 2014). Combining Q methodology with a landscape value typology, and using it to elicit

latent perspectives is a methodological contribution of this dissertation. Q has been applied to reveal peripheral perspectives (Zabala et al. 2018), but never to elicit latent perspectives as done in this dissertation. For all cases where stakeholder perceptions are latent, whether resulting in inertia or not, this approach is applicable.

6.3.3.2 *Methodological contribution: PAR-L*

As discussed in section 6.2.2, a second corollary from Coralita's latent problem status is management inertia. Low threats posed by Coralita to the islands' communities limits reasons for them to adjust the configuration of daily practices that result in Coralita's current manifestation. Just like with Q methodology, the approach here is to address Coralita by proxy, in this case through an adjusted version of participatory action research for latent problems, called PAR-L. Tools such as participatory action research (PAR) have been applied successfully to environmental problems on the community level, e.g., regarding the depletion of fish stocks (Apgar et al. 2017) or disputes about land-use (Valencia et al. 2012). PAR's strength lays in co-creating knowledge, strengthening social networks, generating shared visions and reaching compromises (Trimble and Berkes 2013, Trimble and Lázaro 2014, Apgar et al. 2017). However, PAR generally focusses on manifest problems, which implies conflicts that need to be resolved. But whereas manifest problems come with conflicting stakes that matter to a community, latent environmental problems are characterized by a community's inertia in dealing with them. What this leaves PAR to deal with is not a conflict between highly relevant stakes for PAR but a community's inertia, which is what an adjusted version of PAR was developed for in chapter 4. To resolve the inertia, it addresses a manifest problem with the latent problem as corollary. This approach can be useful for other cases of inertia as well, whether due to latency or not.

Both methodological contributions focus on what people are interested in and ensures their participation by addressing that, rather than trying to get people to act on a topic they do not feel concerned about. In the practical recommendations of chapter 7, these methods will feature again. But first, some reflection on the research setting of this dissertation is in order.

6.4 CONDUCTING RESEARCH IN THE CARIBBEAN: SMALL AND PERSONAL

In the first chapter of this dissertation, the research setting was briefly discussed as a contextual feature of the case focused on: the dealings of a community with Coralita comprised the case researched, which happened to be set on two small Caribbean islands. However, that research setting had some repercussions for the research conducted, due to two main characteristics: the small scale and the Caribbean culture of

Saba and Statia. The implications of these characteristics on the research and how that was dealt with, are discussed in this section, starting with the small scale of both islands.

6.4.1 Implications of the small scale

The most conspicuous characteristic of this dissertation's study area is the small scale. Saba and Statia have a territory of 13 and 21 km², and communities of 2200 and 3300 inhabitants respectively (CBS 2018). What does this imply for the representativeness of the research findings? On the one hand, the small scale of the islands and their history of relative isolation result in a significant idiosyncrasy of Caribbean islands (Crawford 2007, Hillman and D'Agostino 2009). The findings in chapter 4 regarding practices of the Saban community that result in Coralita's current manifestation, can therefore not be assumed to exist on any other Caribbean islands. But the typology of problem statuses derived in that same chapter is applicable to all types of environmental problems, irrespective of where they occur. Also applicable to other locations are the methodological contributions of chapter 3 and 4, regarding Q methodology and PAR-L. The Coralita case on Saba and Statia served merely as an illustration of these approaches, which were designed to be applicable to other cases as well.

The small scale has some methodological advantages. For one, gathering a representative sample of the population is more readily achieved, partly because the amount of people needed to get a representative sample is lower. But also, and this was advantageous for chapter 3 in particular, since it is easier to know the full breadth of opinions present in a community, and to find representatives of them (see Ens et al. 2016). Moreover, actors normally hard to reach are more easily contacted, such as higher government officials. This enabled for example an interview with Statia's then-governor, for chapter 2. And just like the small scale allows for getting a complete picture of the community's perspectives, it also enhances the understanding of the dynamics at play regarding Coralita. The thoroughness of the analysis of daily practices in chapter 4 and the political dynamics in chapter 2 have definitely benefited from this.

An unavoidable implication of conducting research within such small communities for an extended period of time is the footprint left by the researcher on their research subject. The fieldwork for this dissertation spanned three years in total, and the attention drawn to Coralita during that period can be assumed to have had an impact on the local community. As for methodological consequences, the willingness of people to participate in the PAR-L pilot of chapter 4 may have increased following earlier fieldwork campaigns. But since measuring willingness to manage was not a purpose of that chapter, this does not matter. For chapter 3, the relative ranking of Coralita-statements may in theory have been affected by the attention of earlier fieldwork; however, the earlier fieldwork campaign had only lasted one week per island, so its impacts were most probably minimal. Next to methodological implications, the researcher's footprint

raises some ethical questions. However, given the unanimous dislike regarding Coralita that was already present on the island, potential management-encouraging effects of fieldwork could have had little negative impacts.

Lastly, the small scale necessitated some privacy-ensuring measures for the participants at a few instances. For chapter 2, the interviews addressed the delicate topic of governance relationships between The Hague and the islands. And for chapter 4, the participants of the PAR-L pilot were asked to evaluate the social dynamics during the project, but also regarding land-use on Saba in general. To ensure that people felt comfortable to speak freely, interviewees were anonymized in chapter 2, and in chapter 4 evaluation questions were posed during one-on-one interviews rather than focus group sessions. But despite these arrangements, a certain personal dimension can never be fully excluded from the research setting at a scale so small. In the next section, some Caribbean cultural characteristics affecting the research will be looked at as well.

6.4.2 Caribbean island setting

The idiosyncrasy of Caribbean islands in terms of e.g., their history, migratory dynamics, geopolitics and economies, grant them ample scientific attention. For the Dutch islands, authors like Oostindie, Veenendaal and Guadeloupe have addressed these matters extensively, to which this dissertation does not aim to add. But, some characteristics of Caribbean islands in terms of cultural and political dynamics have certainly affected the research conducted, which will be discussed here.

Every research setting comes with cultural characteristics, as is increasingly recognized within the scientific practice. Differences between cultures have for example been acknowledged in the field of international relations, where Meyer (2014) categorized differences across eight work-related dimensions. For example, whether confrontation is avoided, or sought after; whether trust is task-based or relation-based; and whether time is perceived in a linear or circular way. She distinguishes these differences on the level of nations, whereas anthropologist Mary Douglas' Cultural Theory distinguishes four types of "cultural biases" at the level of every institution (Douglas 1999). As for islands, the dependency on international trade, vulnerable economies, and relative isolation, is argued to give rise to "islandness": a strong sense of place and belonging, and a strong identity focused around shared hardship and historic self-sufficiency (Coulthard et al. 2017). Some have even tried to approximate differences between islanders and mainlanders in terms of the Big Five personality test, for example in terms of openness to new experiences (Camperio Ciani et al. 2007, Crawford 2007). Taking a stance on this would be far beyond the scope of this dissertation, but the main point is that the research setting of a Caribbean island comes with specific cultural dynamics, which should be taken into account when conducting research.

Concerning the Caribbean islands that are part of the Dutch kingdom, the differences in style between Caribbean politicians and their counterparts from The Hague receive much attention. Henk Kamp, a former Dutch minister and Kingdom representative, plainly stated that for Dutch politicians following a plan step by step is paramount, whereas on Bonaire improvisation and building relations is more important (Kamp in: Schoenmaeckers 2010, 30). Similarly, looking back at the decades-long process that resulted in the constitutional changes of 2010, Oostindie and Klinkers (2012) refer to Boeli van Leeuwen, the Curaçolanean writer and statesman. Van Leeuwen described the negotiations between politicians from The Hague and the Antilles as half of them playing chess, and the other half dominos: the rules of the game differ entirely. Former governor of Bonaire, Glenn Thodé, puts it differently: the Dutch dance to house, Bonaireans to the bachata; two completely different rhythms (Thodé in: Schoenmaeckers 2010, 30).

The research of this dissertation was mainly affected in one way by the cultural context of the Caribbean islands: the importance of personal relationships over formal ties. Mulder (2016) describes the importance of family and neighbors on Saba, and how these weigh heavier than formal institutions such as the government or professional hierarchies. Explanations for this have been sought in the Caribbean islands' history of colonization and isolation (e.g., Oostindie 2000), making the communities of Saba and Statia mainly rely on themselves. During fieldwork, the importance of participating in island society and building personal relationships with people was quickly noticed. To that end, outreach, educational and volunteering activities were undertaken during each fieldwork campaign. By engaging with the local community in this way, improved understanding of the practices as discussed in chapter 4 was gained, and personal relationships were developed which allowed further research activities. While for the interviews in chapter 2 regarding the governance configuration most interviewees were approached based on their formal position, personal connections were needed for chapter 3. The interviews in that chapter required representatives of the breadth of opinion within the island communities, and were thus mainly recruited via personal connections using the snowball method. Locals met during church services or at community events were asked for participation, and they offered connections with other potential interviewees. Next to engagement activities, the importance of personal connections was also aimed to cater to by conducting research relevant to the local community. Hence, the interview set-up of chapter 2 and 3 was departed from in chapter 4, to make way for a participatory research approach that explicitly aimed to make positive changes to daily Saban practices.

Engaging with the local community in such ways offers a challenge to the need to maintain a degree of objectivity commonly sought after in science. Moreover, it can exacerbate the earlier mentioned impact of a researcher on its research subject. But the conventional image of science being conducted separately from society and striving

for objectivity, is increasingly challenged by perspectives such as post-normal science (Funtowicz and Ravetz 1993). Action research explicitly argues in favor of close collaboration between researcher and researched, and this was built on in chapter 4. Moreover, as was argued at multiple instances, society and IAS cannot be seen separate from each other, and the problem status typology proposed has explicitly social dimensions. The engagements with the local community were therefore both reflective of Saban and Statian reality, and conducive to the research.

6.5 SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

This dissertation introduced a problem status typology, and linked it to policy and management inertia. While chapter 5 confirmed that general link to exist, it was mostly derived from observations regarding one specific case, and the dynamics behind it require more research. Does a latent problem status necessarily mean inertia on the part of the community, or are there examples where people are nevertheless involved in management efforts? Also, a vicious cycle between an absence of stakeholders and policy inertia can be expected to exist: this dissertation framed absent stakeholders as contributing to policy inertia, and therefore aimed to identify stakeholders. But the reverse might work too, as the development of policy will most likely prompt opinions and thus the appearance of stakeholder groups. Additionally, it can be expected that management and policy inertia reinforce each other, and that practices such as discussed in chapter 4 mediate the relationship between problem status and inertia as well. Chapter 5 pointed towards the type of impacts of an invasive alien species as important for whether action occurs or not, and there may be other dynamics involved. The interplay of problem status with other factors influencing the occurrence of inertia is worthwhile researching further.

Regarding the encouragement of action, participatory action research appears very promising, but questions remain regarding the larger scale and long term potential. The people involved with PAR-L in chapter 4 were those who care about the Coralita issue and are willing to put effort into projects regarding land-use. Is PAR-L versatile enough to cater to everyone's interests, and still reach the aim of lifting inertia regarding Coralita? Also related to PAR, the influence of external conveners should receive more attention: chapter 4 discusses the leadership of the researcher as crucial to the project's success, so what is the durability of such projects (see Barnes and van Laerhoven 2015)?

A knowledge gap that kept coming up throughout the research as key to the Coralita issue, is the low predictability of the vine's impacts. Inherent to the definition of a latent problem, is the limited predictability of the problem's impact, for which this dissertation offered avenues to work around. Although linking the latent problem to a manifest

problem showed potential to redeem inertia, more ecological knowledge regarding Coralita is needed to inform management measures. Thus, increasing understanding of the vine's impacts would certainly be a valuable direction of future research, which can build on Sweeney's (2018) work that links Coralita's characteristics to Saba's ecosystems and gauges potential damage from that.

Lastly, the Caribbean context which was referred to earlier in section 6.4 prompts some remaining questions. As mentioned in chapter 2, the merits of a polycentric system may materialize differently in a Caribbean context. As Nauta (2011) suggests, the scale and history of Caribbean societies might call for a different division of governmental powers, and for a reconsideration of the general understanding that every public task can in theory be assigned to a local entity. Another aspect that would be interesting to research further is the way people relate to nature. Research into human-nature relationships has shown that differences across cultures exist (Duong and Van Den Born 2019), which for example can imply a lower tendency to control nature. Locals sometimes expressed a somewhat *laissez-faire* attitude towards nature, pointing out that in a hurricane-prone area trying to control your environment is a lost cause. This can be assumed to affect attitudes towards management of invasive alien species, and would make for interesting future research.